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Remote Collaboration of the University-School in the Organization of Student Teaching Practice

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Abstract

The article analyzes the issues of remote collaboration of the university-school in the organization of students' pedagogical practice. In conditions of extreme situations and territorial remoteness of educational institutions and universities, the organization of collaboration is possible only in a remote format. At the same time, there is a tendency towards the use of digital technologies in the higher education system, while their use is often ignored in the framework of pedagogical practice. The study reveals the possibilities of organizational and methodological support of students' pedagogical practice using distance educational technologies. The article demonstrates the advantages of distance collaboration of the university-school in the organization of students' pedagogical practice, which implies the organization of joint activities of the participants of pedagogical practice both in the absence and in the presence of territorial restrictions. The article analyzes the implementation of a practice-oriented approach to the professional training of a future teacher in the higher education system, describes the methodological and normative basis of the practical training of students. The role of collaboration between institutions of vocational education and general education in the process of organizing pedagogical practice is revealed. The leading methods in the study of this problem were questionnaires and content analysis, which made it possible to identify deficiencies in the content and organizational aspects of the university-school collaboration. The article describes the functions and principles of the remote collaboration of the university-school, revealing the substantive basis of the organizational and methodological support of students' pedagogical practice.

Keywords: pedagogical practice, university-school collaboration, remote collaboration, distance educational technologies, functions of distance interaction, principles of distance interaction, online course.

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Introduction

The challenges of the present time have determined the need for the development and application of distance educational technologies in the process of training future teachers. According to the data provided by the Ministry of Science and Higher Education of the Russian Federation (2021), under the extreme conditions of 2020, pedagogical universities have accumulated innovative experience in organizing training for students in a distance format. At the same time, in contrast to the improvements of the teaching process using distance educational technologies, deficiencies of distant technologies application within the framework of pedagogical practice are revealed. The implementation of the university-school collaboration is the key condition for organizing pedagogical practice as an indicator of the quality of future teachers training. The remote format of collaboration opens up new opportunities for normative, theoretical, methodological, informational and psychological-pedagogical support of a student and a teacher in the process of pedagogical practice, both in extreme conditions and given the distance barriers, and in the traditional mode of teaching students. The use of digital educational resources that ensure openness, accessibility and ease of communication for participants during practical training necessitates scientific substantiation of the functions and principles as a methodological basis for implementation of the university-school collaboration distantly.

Purpose and objectives of the study

Research purpose is to identify the functions and principles of remote collaboration of the university-school in the process of organizing the teaching practice of students. The process of professional training of a teacher in the higher education system was studied. The authors set to identify the functions and principles of remote collaboration of the university-school in the process of organizing student teaching practice.

Literature review

In scientific research, the problem of organizing pedagogical practice of students is represented by a wide range of works. A number of studies are devoted to the training of teaching staff in the higher education system according to the practice-oriented approach (Bayborodova, 2015; Ledovskaya, 2018; Fedina, Burmykina, Ziyautdinov, Kretova, & Smirnova, 2016). The mechanism for implementing the practice-oriented approach in higher education is pedagogical practice.

In accordance with the Federal State Educational Standard of Higher Education – bachelor's degree in the field of study 44.03.01 Pedagogical education (Ministry of Science and Higher Education of the Russian Federation, 2018), practice is an integral component of the main professional educational program of higher education, an obligatory part of the curriculum. According to Guruzhapov & Margolis (2014), the implementation of a practice-oriented approach implies a significant increase in the volume of practice. In accordance with this, the authors proposed, firstly, to change the requirements for the results of the main professional educational program on the basis of bringing the competencies mastered by students in line with the labor functions of the professional standard of a teacher. Secondly, Guruzhapov & Margolis (2014) substantiated the change in the structure of the main professional educational program from disciplinary to modular. At the same time, the module should be significantly strengthened by the share of practice on a clinical basis (in the conditions of a real educational organization).

Currently, the emphasis of the practice-oriented approach is shifting from pedagogical practice to practical training. According to the Order of the Ministry of Science and Higher Education of the Russian Federation and the Ministry of Education of the Russian Federation (2020) "On the practical training of students", practical training is carried out during practice and during the implementation of academic subjects, courses, disciplines (modules). Practical training is organized through practical classes, tutorials, laboratory work and other similar types of educational activities, which also provides for the modernization of the design process of the main professional educational program of higher education.

The need to take into account the practice-oriented approach when designing the main educational program and discipline programs is emphasized in the publication by Bayborodova (2015). The author pays special attention to the organization of students' pedagogical practice, which ensures the relationship between theoretical and practical training of future teachers.

In the study by Fedina et al. (2016) the problems of pedagogical practice are considered through the description of the model of continuous pedagogical practice from the first to the fourth/fifth training course of future teachers and throughout the entire period of training of future masters. The authors proposed ways to solve the problems of pedagogical practice: the development of regulatory documents for the implementation of the model of continuous pedagogical practice, the definition of criteria for the selection of educational organizations, the creation of the concept of an information portal for posting information about the practice and training of bachelors (masters) in the pedagogical area.

In the article by Ledovskaya (2018), the logic of implementing a practice-oriented approach can be seen both in the increase in the amount of hours (credits) for the practical training of students and the continuity of all types of practices, and in the content aspect of organizing students' practice (variability of assignments, individualization, forms of control and assessment). According to the author, a feature of the organization of students' practice is the network interaction of vocational education and general education institutions.

The collaboration of the university-school is the basis for the organization of students' pedagogical practice. Guruzhapov & Margolis (2014) note that the purpose of such collaboration is to enhance the practical training of students. Supporting this idea, Lyubimova & Borisov (2015) note that the key figure in the collaboration of the university-school is the student, and a significant part of the efforts in cooperation with the school should be directed to the formation of a future teacher who, in the process of networking, gains professional experience in practice. The authors propose to strengthen the practical training of students in the pedagogical area by increasing their practical employment in the process of network cooperation with the school while changing the forms and methods of presenting theoretical material – using remote courses.

The need to support students' pedagogical practice using distance learning technologies is explained by a number of reasons.

Firstly, the remote collaboration of the university-school in the process of pedagogical practice must be carried out not only in the traditional (full-time) mode of teaching students, but also in conditions of the extreme situation and the territorial remoteness of schools from pedagogical university. Describing the experience of using distance educational technologies in the organization of students' pedagogical practice, Solovyova (2011) draws attention to the fact that the success of using distance technologies depends on the degree of development of specific forms, methods and techniques of distance learning. By organizing pedagogical practice using distance learning technologies, it becomes possible to invite for cooperation teachers-methodologists who satisfy both professional level and geographic requests from any point covered by the Internet. This is due to such features of distance education as flexibility, modularity, parallelism, long-range action, asynchrony, coverage, and profitability (Solovyova, 2011).

Secondly, the education system is at the stage of digital transformation, and informational changes are inevitable in the process of training future teachers. The process of digitalization of the education system is influenced by a number of factors. Kondakov & Sergeev (2021) name such factors as the development of

digital technologies, each of them has its own didactic potential; the formation of an information society and a network model of organizing life, which changes the system of values at the level of an individual, social institutions; the emergence and prospect of domination of the "digital generation"; the formation of a digital economy with new forms of work organization (work in remote access, distributed project teams, and others). The authors note that the humanitarian nature of education requires taking into account the person-centered nature of the digital educational environment, which is not so much a set of resources and services as a networked environment for education, socialization, identity formation, student personality development, in a variety of forms and types of activities, which translates a certain system of objective knowledge, values and norms (Kondakov & Sergeev, 2021).

Thus, an effective way of organizing joint activities of participants of pedagogical practice in full-time and remote modes is the remote collaboration of the university-school. Talking about remote interaction, we are talking not only about video conferencing, mailing via e-mail, cloud technologies (Google), information storages containing educational materials on specific subjects and sections of pedagogical practice. The remote collaboration of the university-school is aimed at organizing the joint activities of the participants of pedagogical practice in such a way when everyone acts autonomously, independently, in an individual mode and schedule, taking into account the goals of joint activities. At the same time, there is an exchange of pedagogical experience, enrichment of educational content, feedback on the intermediate and final results of joint activities (Korotkov, 2003).

Methodology

Approaches

The theoretical and methodological basis of the study was formed by methodological approaches (axiological, competence-based, system-activity) and the didactic concept of digital vocational education and training.

The axiological approach reveals the processes of purposeful formation of basic value beliefs and "nationally identical code in the process of digital transformation of the education system" (Gordienko, Sokolova, & Simonova, 2019), determines the awareness and assignment of pedagogical values-goals, values-means in the course of joint activities of participants of practice in order to master the meaning-making, individual creative professional activities. The system of values determines the content of the main directions of the personal and professional development of the future teacher and remote collaboration of the university-school.

The competence-based approach allows, in the process of mastering students' professional activities, to form their readiness and ability to independently and responsibly solve educational, life and professional tasks. Competencies are a combination of traits, abilities, and attitudes. An important task in the training of a teacher in the higher education system is to bring the existing list of mastered competencies, specified in the Federal State Educational Standard of Higher Education (2018), into line with labor actions specified by the Professional Standard of a Teacher (Ministry of Education of the Russian Federation, 2013).

The system-activity approach acts as a methodological basis for students mastering professional activities during practice and allows to understand that the professional activity of a teacher is an activity that integrates the ways of implementing various labor functions and labor actions that a student masters based on the assimilation of ideals, values, moral attitudes, moral norms (Margolis, 2019). The professional activity of a teacher is not a set of techniques and methods; it is a complex type of activity that involves the building of a system of educational relations, taking into account changing conditions. Thus, the coordination of axiological and system-activity approaches to the organization of remote collaboration of the university-school is achieved. At the same time, the activities of various participants of practice (teacher-student-teacher) should be coordinated with the leading role of the university.

The didactic concept of digital vocational education and training (Bilenko et al., 2019) describes the content of the didactic principles of digital educational process of vocational education, the possibilities of distance educational technologies, the functions of the participants of interaction in the course of the implementation of the digital educational process of vocational education.

Research methods

The theoretical methods such as analysis of psychological, pedagogical and methodological literature, generalization of the pedagogical experience in the implementation of distance educational technologies in the process of training future teachers and organizing the student pedagogical practice were used. The following empirical methods were used: content analysis of the curricula, internship programs, funds of assessment tools, student reports on the results of internship; survey of students, university lecturers and teachers.

In the course of the research, a content analysis of 30 curricula was carried out in the field of study 44.03.01 "Pedagogical education", 21 programs of industrial practice "On the formation of professional skills and experience of professional activity", funds of appraisal tools and student reports.

Content analysis was carried out according to the following criteria: the number of assigned competencies for practice; correspondence of the fund of appraisal means to the formed competences; orientation of the content of internship programs to the labor functions of the professional standard of a teacher, implemented by students in the course of pedagogical practice; elaboration of recommendations for organizational and methodological support of the practice process.

Based on the content analysis, the features of the content of pedagogical practice and the specifics of its organization were identified, which formed the basis of the developed questionnaire.

The questionnaire was developed by the authors of the study, analyzed by an expert group, reviewed and approved by the Scientific and Methodological Council of the Volgograd State Social and Pedagogical University. Three variants of questionnaires, identical in content, addressed to participants of pedagogical practice were proposed to students, teachers and lecturers. Each version of the questionnaire consisted of three sections. In the first section, the respondents were asked to assess the degree of students' readiness to undergo practical training: professional and motivational readiness for the implementation of pedagogical activities, provision of information, didactic and other necessary materials. The second section was aimed at studying the process of accompanying students by university teachers and teachers of educational institutions, as well as studying the process of interaction between teachers. The third section involved assessing the quality of the organization of pedagogical practice: the volume and content of assignments for pedagogical practice, compliance of the practice schedule with the educational process of the educational organization, drawing up reporting documentation based on the results of the practice.

The questionnaire was answered by 183 students of 2-5 courses of bachelor's degree, studying in the direction 44.03.01 "Pedagogical education", 40 lecturers and 36 teachers assisting students with the pedagogical practice. The sample of the study was formed from the number of students, university teachers and teachers of educational organizations who participated in the production practice "On the formation of professional skills and experience of professional activity" and who wished to take part in an anonymous study. The survey was carried out in Google Forms, which provided an opportunity to involve students and teachers who are located in conditions of territorial remoteness from the university. Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

The answers received were subjected to a qualitative analysis aimed at studying the content and organizational characteristics of the university-school implementation.

Results

The analysis of the data obtained during the survey made it possible to determine the content and organizational aspects of the university-school implementation, which can be solved more effectively in a distance format.

The substantial aspect of the collaboration of the university-school in the process of teaching practice

The results of the survey showed that it is necessary to strengthen the consistency of the activities of university teachers and teachers of educational organizations in determining the content of pedagogical practice, aimed at the formation of competencies in students, taking into account the labor functions of the teacher and the real situation of pedagogical reality in the region. Autonomous work on the content can lead to the “disintegration” of practice into separate tasks, the absence of a single logical line in the student’s practical training. The results of the questionnaire showed a number of difficulties in the content aspect of pedagogical practice, requiring the solution of the following tasks:

- minimize the gap between the practical training of students at the university and the requirements of real labor activity in an educational institution;
- create conditions for preventing professional difficulties at the stage of entering the profession;
- ensure the individualization of the practical training of students, taking into account the experience of a particular educational institution (variable tasks, the choice of types of activities, the definition of pedagogical tools, taking into account the base of practice);
- provide opportunities for acquaintance of all participants of the university-school collaboration with the innovative experience of the pedagogical activity of the region.

Collaboration in the “teacher - student - teacher” triad within the framework of pedagogical practice has its limitations, which were identified during the survey. In conditions of territorial remoteness of an educational institution, the possibilities for organizing feedback are minimal; students, university professors and teachers of educational institutions do not always have the opportunity to communicate, discuss and clarify certain issues in the process of practice. When organizing collaboration and the process of supporting pedagogical practice, it is necessary to solve the following tasks:

- ensuring the availability of all necessary information, methodological, pedagogical materials for the practice of both students and teachers of educational institutions and the ability to interact with participants of pedagogical practice both before its start and at any of its stages;

- the possibility of more effective planning of students' practical activities and the process of its accompaniment by the teacher; determining what specific support a teacher or other specialists of an educational institution can provide to a student;
- strengthening the importance of the role of a mentor (both a teacher-mentor and university teachers) in the process of students' pedagogical practice: joint participation of university teachers and teachers of educational institutions in preparing students for the implementation of pedagogical activities, monitoring the process and results of the practice assignments (visiting and analyzing lessons, preparation of abstracts, development and implementation of extracurricular activities and other activities);
- increasing pedagogical reflection and active position of future teachers in the process of personal and professional development.

The organizational aspect of the university-school collaboration in the process of teaching practice

A survey of students, teachers of educational institutions, and university professors showed the presence of difficulties in the organization of teaching practice. There is some inconsistency between the timetable for the internship of a particular student with the planning of the teacher's work. On the one hand, a teacher cannot always be present at school even at open lessons and student events if the educational institution is located at a distance from the university. On the other hand, the specifics of the tasks of pedagogical practice may not correspond to the educational process of the school (for example, holding an event that is not included in the schedule of the educational institution). Difficulties in document circulation are noted both at the stage of sending students to pedagogical practice and at the stage of its completion (preparation of student reporting documentation and its verification and assessment by teachers).

To overcome the identified problems in the organization of the collaboration of the university-school at all stages of pedagogical practice, it is necessary to use digital educational resources that ensure openness, accessibility and ease of communication. In this regard, there is the need for a scientific understanding of the functions (purpose - for what?) and principles (as a rule, requirement - how?) of the university-school remote collaboration in the organization of students' pedagogical practice.

On the basis of the conducted meta-analysis and taking into account the empirical data of the study, the main functions of distance university-school implementation in the course of pedagogical practice were determined:

- 1) The information function contributes to the presentation of up-to-date information to students and teachers on the main directions of education development, new pedagogical technologies, educational programs. It is aimed at informing students and teachers about the content of the practice program, its temporary, organizational, structural components, and is aimed at increasing the level of formation of the regulatory, legal, managerial competencies of teachers.
- 2) The methodological function involves the creation of educational and methodological complexes to accompany students and teachers in the course of pedagogical practice, the development of methodological recommendations, manuals on topical applied problems of practical training in higher education.
- 3) The function of experience exchange is aimed at discussing didactic and methodological issues of education by teachers, at acquainting students with examples of advanced, innovative pedagogical experience. This function helps to stimulate the creative initiative and professional growth of all participants of practice (teachers, students), the teacher's mastery of the experience of the role of a mentor in the information and educational space of the university-school.
- 4) The evaluation function contributes to the continuous assessment of the success of the student at the university throughout the practice, provides instant feedback, objectivity and transparency in the assessment of assignments; involves organizing and conducting peer review of practice programs.
- 5) The corrective function ensures that the expectations and capabilities of the student are aligned with the requirements of the professional environment and changing working conditions. It is aimed at minimizing personal and professional difficulties for the future teacher at the stage of entering the profession, overcoming various types of barriers that hinder the successful implementation of pedagogical activities.

The key principles of the university-school remote collaboration in organizing the teaching practice of students are (Korotkov, 2003):

- 1) The principle of openness presupposes overcoming the closed pedagogical, sometimes uncontrolled by the teacher, interaction between a student and a teacher in the educational organization on the basis of which the practice is carried out; active communication of a student,

teacher in the course of completing practice assignments; the possibility and availability of control and provision of pedagogical support to students and teachers from the university.

This principle ensures mutual exchange of information and equal rights to use it, directness and “honesty” of all participants of pedagogical practice.

- 2) The principle of accessibility, on the one hand, allows each participant in the collaboration to act independently in an individual mode and a convenient schedule, to provide unlimited access to the educational content of the pedagogical practice program and educational and methodological support of students, teachers. On the other hand, this principle assumes the ability to control pace, content of the student's personal and professional development, allows to take into account the peculiarities of the specialty, form of study, course, group, provides a consistent transition in the course of performing tasks in practice from simple to complex and from complex to simple, from general to the particular and from the particular to the general, from the individual to the group and from the group to the individual.
- 3) The principle of responsibility is manifested in the implementation of formal and informal control over the course of activities of all participants of practice for the purpose of timely corrective intervention. This principle acts as a constraint on freedom, understood as self-will in relation to the program of practice, its process, the procedure and form of reporting.
- 4) The principle of compatibility (analogous to the didactic principle of interactivity) requires the construction of distance interaction based on active multilateral communication – real and network – between a teacher and a student of the university, between a pupil and a school teacher, between a teacher and a teacher.
- 5) The principle of autonomy focuses on the independent educational and professional activities of a student in a digital educational environment and assumes the student's ability to independently choose a strategy, pace, methods of completing practice assignments; allows a teacher to track the personal development indicators and educational results of students.

Discussion

The functions and principles formulated above set the need to create the necessary and sufficient conditions for the productive collaboration of the participants of pedagogical practice in the educational space of the university-school:

- creation of a network of basic schools of the university under certain conditions: staffing (readiness of the teaching staff for remote and face-to-face interaction, the degree of their motivation to work with students, the presence of the highest category of professional activity among most of the teachers, experience of participation in project, innovative activities); material and technical support for the demonstration of advanced pedagogical experience to students (modern school equipment, the possibility of using distance learning technologies);
- search for motivational mechanisms for teachers accompanying students during practice (considers at the regional level the possibility of including work with students in the certification of teachers as a criterion for the effectiveness of professional activities, etc.);
- creation on the basis of the university of the center for scientific and methodological support of teachers, which resolves issues of scientific and methodological, organizational and pedagogical support for the practical training of students with the involvement of teachers-winners of professional skills competitions, teachers with experience in innovative activities, representatives of subject and methodological associations and associations of the region;
- development of an online course as a tool for organizational and methodological support of students' pedagogical practice, which accumulates the identified functions and principles. An online course is a way of organizing the educational process or its separate part using electronic or distance learning technologies (Bilenko et al., 2019). As a mandatory part of the main professional educational program of higher education, teaching practice differs from lectures and seminars in a fundamentally important characteristic – the need to include teachers in the educational process of students. In this regard, the online course, understood as a “method of organizing the educational process”, fulfills the task of real inclusion of teachers in the organizational and methodological support of students during pedagogical practice, as well as the task of effective interaction of the “teacher – student – teacher” triad as in extreme conditions and the territorial remoteness of schools from the pedagogical university, and in the traditional mode of teaching students.

Conclusion

In the course of the study, the content of pedagogical practice has been updated from the standpoint of system-activity and axiological approaches to the practical training of a future teacher as priority scientific approaches in education. Practical training of a future teacher involves mastering, in the course of educational and professional activities, professional competencies that correlate with the professional

functions and labor actions of the teacher. At the same time, it is important that the content of pedagogical practice should be aimed not at developing individual techniques, methods but at mastering the experience of solving problems of organizing various aspects of educational relations.

The results of the study confirmed that this requires the interaction of university teachers, teachers and methodologists of schools in the region in the process of developing practice programs, assignments, assessment tools, and other teaching materials.

Scientific comprehension of the provisions of digital didactics, the essential characteristics of the digital educational environment, analysis of the results of an empirical study on the substantive and organizational support of the practical training of students in the higher education system contributed to the identification of the functions and principles of distance interaction between the university and the school in the process of organizing the pedagogical practice of students. The main functions of remote interaction are informational, methodological, exchange of experience, evaluation, correctional. Key principles of remote interaction are openness, accessibility, responsibility, compatibility, and autonomy.

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Competing interests

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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